

POWDER-FORGING OF SiC PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) possess excellent properties; however, cost remains a barrier to adopting them for wide applications. The powder-forging process in the atmosphere to produce SiC particulate reinforced aluminum alloy composites into a near-net shape has been investigated. This technique would make it possible to manufacture low-cost MMCs. Forging the powder mixture of SiC particulate and 2024 aluminum alloy powder, oxidation of the aluminum alloy powder surface during heating became a problem. Electron probe micro analysis indicated that Mg, the alloying element in the aluminum alloy powder, was oxidized preferentially, and that this oxidation took place to a lesser degree at temperatures below 673 K but much more at 773 K. Mg contributes to precipitation strengthening in the aluminum alloy. The decrease of solute Mg content in the aluminum alloy powder due to the oxidation was thought to result in degradation of the composite strength. Therefore, the powder mixture was first preliminary-forged at temperatures below 673 K to increase the density to some extent, then finish-forging was carried out at a temperature just below the solidus line. This process has suppressed the oxidation of Mg and has achieved 100% densification. As a result, the tensile strength of powder-forged composites has been improved.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Composite; Matrix, Aluminum; Silicon Carbide; Manufacturing; Powder-Forging.

1. INTRODUCTION

SiC particulate reinforced aluminum alloy composites (SiCp/Al) provide excellent specific modulus, specific strength, heat resistance, wear

resistance and also, small thermal expansion, and these outstanding properties have been attracting the industry's attention. However, their use is currently restricted by high cost. In order to overcome the problem, melt stirring [1], spray co-deposition [2], and other production methods have been under development as economical manufacturing processes. Moreover, in order to improve the strength of SiCp/Al, refinement of SiC particulate would be an effective answer. The powder metallurgical process allows fine particulate less than $10 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter to disperse in aluminum more smoothly than in other processes, so we can expect to manufacture high performance materials. The powder-forging technique in the powder metallurgical process allows direct forming of powders into a near-net shape and rarely requires subsequent machining, resulting in good material yield and simple processes. In this study, investigation has been made on the process of forming SiCp/Al by powder-forging in the atmosphere in an attempt to develop an economical manufacturing process for forgings.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The SiC particulate consists of α -type with an average diameter of $5 \mu\text{m}$. The 2024 aluminum alloy powder was produced by the air atomizing process. First, SiC particulate and aluminum alloy powder were blended and an aluminum alloy powder mixture containing 20% SiC particulate in the volume fraction was obtained. This powder mixture was forged at various temperatures and under various pressure conditions in the atmosphere. The forgings were heat-treated (T6) and then subjected to tensile tests. The distribution of alloying elements in the aluminum alloy powder and forgings was examined by EPMA. The content of oxygen in forgings was determined by the inert gas fusion method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Oxidation of Mg in the Aluminum Alloy Powder Aluminum alloy powder has an Al_2O_3 film on its powder surface. Hot plastic working is effective to break up the Al_2O_3 film, diffuse atoms, and bond both the aluminum alloy powders and the aluminum alloy powder with the SiC particulate. On the other hand, aluminum alloy powder is likely to be oxidized during heating, and it is estimated that particularly Mg in the aluminum alloy is more likely to be oxidized. Therefore, the distribution of Mg in aluminum alloy powder was examined by EPMA when the powder mixture was heated at the four temperatures of 473 K, 573 K, 673 K, and 773 K for one hour at each temperature.

Before heating, the Mg was almost uniformly distributed all over the

FIGURE 1. Distribution of Mg in the 2024 aluminum alloy powder before heating.

FIGURE 2. Distribution of Mg in the 2024 aluminum alloy powder heated at 773 K for 1 hour.

cross section of aluminum alloy powder, as shown in Figure 1, and the Mg distribution in the aluminum alloy powder heated at 673 K or lower was similar to that before heating. However, when heated to 773 K, Mg concentrated at the surface of the aluminum alloy powder as shown in Figure 2, and the Mg content in the aluminum alloy powder was markedly reduced, as compared with that before heating. This phenomenon is assumed to result from oxidation of Mg during heating, which generates MgO on the powder surface. At 773 K, the diffusion coefficient of Mg in aluminum is $1.05 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ [3] and the diffusing distance $(2Dt)^{1/2}$ (D: diffusion coefficient, t: time) of Mg for one hour is estimated to be $28 \mu\text{m}$, indicating that Mg can well diffuse aluminum alloy powder with average radius of $20 \mu\text{m}$. The standard formation free energy of 2MgO is low compared with that of $2/3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, thus causing Mg to be oxidized extremely easily.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the temperatures at which 20% SiCp/2024 powder mixture was heated and the intensity of Mg $K\alpha$ inside the 2024 powder by using EPMA. No change was found in Mg content at 673 K or below but the Mg content markedly decreased when heated at 773 K.

FIGURE 3. Relationship between heating temperature of 20%SiCp/2024 powder mixture and intensity of Mg $K\alpha$ inside the 2024 powder.

Mg as well as Cu are principal alloying elements for precipitation strengthening in the 2024 aluminum alloy. The age hardening behavior of aluminum alloys varies with the Mg content [4]. It is assumed that if solute Mg in the aluminum alloy powder decreases due to oxidation, sufficient strength cannot be achieved in the forged and heat-treated (T6) 20%SiCp/2024 since the effect of precipitation strengthening decreases. For this reason, it is essential to suppress oxidation of Mg in powder-forging of SiCp/2024.

3.2 Two-Stage Powder-Forging Various means can be employed to suppress Mg oxidation. In this study, two-stage powder-forging was attempted on the condition that the forging be performed in the atmosphere. First, at 623 K, which is in the temperature range where oxidation of Mg can be ignored, the powder mixture underwent preliminary-forging to increase the relative density in the range 62.0 to 93.8%, then it was heated to 773 K to achieve 100% density by finish-forging. Figure 4 shows the relationships between the relative density of materials preliminary-forged at 623 K and the tensile

FIGURE 4. Relationships between relative density of materials preliminary-forged at 623 K and tensile properties of the materials after finish-forging for 20%SiCp/2024.

FIGURE 5. Optical micrograph of 20%SiCp/2024 powder-forged and heat-treated (T6).

properties of the material after finish-forging. Both ultimate tensile strength and the 0.2% yield strength increased as the density of preliminary-forged material was increased. The strength of the material, which was produced by heating the cold compacted powder mixture directly to 773 K and forging without preliminary-forging at 623 K, decreased as compared with that of the two-stage forgings. The elastic modulus was the same level under any forging conditions.

The microstructure of powder-forged 20%SiCp/2024 is shown in Figure 5. The porosity was not observed for any material produced under any conditions. Because a simple blending process was used, SiC particulate seems to aggregate at the aluminum alloy powder interface. However, in actuality, aluminum alloy flows into the spaces among the SiC particulate, causing the SiC particulate to disperse.

The determination of oxygen content in the finish-forgings indicated that the oxygen content increased as the density of preliminary-forgings was decreased, as shown in Figure 6. It appears that when the density of preliminary-forgings is low, air tends to flow into the spaces among the aluminum alloy powders and oxidizes the Mg in aluminum alloys during heating at 773 K, probably increasing the oxygen content. When heating in a vacuum, it has also been reported that the moisture on the aluminum alloy powder surface reacts with Mg to generate MgO [5]. However, because our study has found that the oxygen content varies with the density of preliminary-forgings, it seemed that reactions of Mg with oxygen in the atmosphere were dominant. As Mg in aluminum alloys is oxidized, the effect of precipitation strengthening decreases to lower

FIGURE 6. Relationship between relative density of materials preliminary-forged at 623 K and oxygen content in the finish-forgings for 20%SiCp/2024.

FIGURE 7. Relationship between tensile strength and oxygen content for 20%SiCp/2024.

the strength. In addition, generation of MgO may weaken the interface of Al/Al or Al/SiC. Consequently, as shown in Figure 4, it is estimated that the strength decreased, as the preliminary-forgings had low density, and as the density of the preliminary-forgings was increased, strength increased because oxidation of Mg was suppressed. Figure 7 showed the relationship between strength and the content of oxygen. The decrease in the oxygen content corresponded well to the increase in strength.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) In powder-forging SiCp/Al, it is essential to suppress oxidation of Mg in aluminum alloys.
- 2) Oxidation of Mg in aluminum alloy powder took place to a lesser degree at temperatures below 673 K but excessively at 773 K.
- 3) The powder mixture was first preliminary-forged at temperatures below 673 K to increase the density to some extent, then finish-forged at 773 K. This two-stage powder-forging process has suppressed oxidation of Mg and has achieved 100% densification. As a result, the strength of the composites has been improved.

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